

Implementation of Unobtrusive Sensing Technology to support Informal Caregivers for elderly care

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Abstract. There is an increasing worldwide demand for technology-driven assistive systems to support informal caregivers. In response, the present work explores, evaluates and implements unobtrusive sensing technology for monitoring real-time elderly behavior. It conducts a state-of-the-art review to explore advantages and disadvantages of pre-existing unobtrusive sensor systems (USSs) for monitoring human activity and behavior. Next, it develops and evaluates an unobtrusive multi-sensing system for tracing and tracking elderly behavior. Finally, it prototypes a persuasive communication/coaching platform, which will act as a channel between USSs and caregivers

Keywords: Unobtrusive sensing, Informal caregivers, Persuasive Technology

1 Introduction and background

The world population is aging at an alarming rate. By the year 2050, approximately 16% of the world's population will be considered as elderly [1]. This rise will be challenging for the available medical care services. Providing care to elderly who are staying alone or are suffering from chronic illnesses can be burdensome for informal caregivers [2]. While informal caregiving is required and promoted, its effects on caregivers are detrimental. The literature has delineated its impact on physical health, emotional well-being, social life and financial condition of the informal caregivers. A general lack of support for informal caregiving was found, leading to emotional and physical illnesses [3, 4].

Many solutions were explored to help caregivers maintain their well-being and assist them in caregiving process [5, 6]. Sensor-based technology for monitoring physical, physiological, and emotional activities of the elderly is state-of-the-art [7, 8]. These technology-driven solutions are intelligent in data management, are scalable and enable care from a distance. While efforts are being made to make sensor-based systems technologically reliable, discernible attempts are also being made to ensure their user acceptability [9]. Most of these systems are wearable in nature which creates uneasiness, resulting in higher rejection rate from the elderly.

A step further, the concept of using non-invasive/ambient/unobtrusive sensors for monitoring daily life activities is novel. Seemingly, UST is a sensor-based technology that detects change in the surroundings without demanding much of user's attention. Research has acclaimed the use of unobtrusive sensors for monitoring physical, physiological, and emotional human behaviour [10]. USSs overcome the drawbacks of wearable sensing systems, resulting in high acceptability with improved user experience. While the idea of using USS seems promising, thorough research on its effective implementation is required.

Aim: The goal of this doctoral research is to evaluate USS for optimizing their successful implementation among informal caregivers and elderly. To achieve this, initially the gaps in real-life implementation of USS will be identified. Further, a USS for tracking and tracing relevant behaviors (e.g. nocturnal unrest) of elderly will be developed. Reliability and accuracy of USS will be tested in lab and real-life settings. Lastly, to disseminate the information of elderly behavior changes collected by USS to (in)formal caregivers, a persuasive online communication

platform will be prototyped. While designing this platform, a user-centered approach with persuasive technology will be used. This platform can be used to coach both elderlies and caregivers.

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2 Research design and Methodology

The research is divided into three major phases - Exploratory, Testing & Evaluation, and, Design. Currently, a state-of-the-art review and preparation for testing and evaluation phase is in progress.

Exploratory phase: A state-of-the-art review aims to explore advantages and disadvantages of existing USSs. The proposed research questions are:

1. How is the concept of unobtrusiveness defined and evaluated in existing literature?
2. What types of Unobtrusive Sensing Systems (USSs) used for monitoring physical and emotional behavior changes of human adults can be identified?
3. What are the opportunities and limitations in terms of feasibility, reliability, accuracy, and acceptability of identified USSs in lab and field studies?

Methods: Scopus, Web of Science (WOS), and ACM digital library databases were used to conduct state-of-the-art review. For searching titles, keywords and abstracts were used. Studies from the last ten years (2011-2020) mentioning unobtrusive/contactless/non-wearable/wireless sensing systems in monitoring or recognizing emotional and physical human behavior were included. Review papers and studies including subjects below age 18 and animals were excluded. This search yielded a total of 2331 papers for title and abstract screening.

Testing and Evaluation Phase: To understand more issues on practical application of USS, unobtrusive sensors based on WiFi, mmWave, and depth-sensing technology to measure/detect/monitor human behaviors and activities will be deployed. The research questions are:

- Lab testing with healthy adults: What is the accuracy and reliability of the different USSs while detecting relevant physical behavior changes?
- Real-life testing in elderly care homes: What is the reliability and feasibility of the designed multi-sensor USS for elderly?

Methods: Evaluation of USS in lab settings with participants enacting relevant behaviours (determined by interviews with informal caregivers) will be performed. A-B testing among sensors will also be done. USS will then be deployed in elderly home to test feasibility in daily usages followed by a feedback and interviews with elderly and informal caregivers to get insights on acceptability.

Design Phase: The aim is to prototype a Lo-Fi persuasive communication/coaching platform driven by data obtained from USS. The platform will act as real-time information and feedback channel between USS, (in)formal caregivers and elderlies. The platform will be evaluated for its user experience and persuasiveness with (in)formal caregivers and elderlies. The research questions are:

- What are the expectations and barriers of (in)formal caregivers and elderlies towards persuasive communication/coaching platform integrated with USSs?

- How the persuasive technology can be used in the design flow of Lo-Fi pro- to-type of a communication system for providing the real-time information of elder-lies to (in)formal caregivers?

Methods: A mixed method research with participatory development design approach (CeHRes roadmap) will be used for creating the platform. Qualitative and quantitative methods will be used to identify needs and barriers of informal caregivers and elderlies towards such platforms.

3 Preliminary Results

State-of-the-art review: At present, abstract screening is in process but a few interesting points noted so far. The definition of "Unobtrusive Sensing" varies across the literature. The term is easily misinterpreted and used for both wearables and non-wearable technologies. For example, Galvanic Skin Response sensors for emotion detection, inertial sensors for fall detection etc. were attached to the users body and called unobtrusive systems. Whereas on the other hand sensing systems which require no physical contact and attention like Wi-fi, radar etc. were termed as unobtrusive systems. This requires a more clear definition of "Unobtrusive sensing" considering its importance in the implementation. A major focus is given to fall detection, vital sign detection (heart rate and respiratory rate) and sleep monitoring in the literature, but a system which can include major relevant activities at once is desirable from both economic and user prospective. The measurement of physiological activities is done mostly using wearable sensors, which might not fit in elderly health monitoring. Lastly, number of studies with interesting ideas like use of wifi signals to vital signs etc. were marked for unobtrusive monitoring. But they have demonstrated only lab testing which is not informative to estimate the implementation challenges in real life.

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